

Biodiversity within the “Environment” theme of the 7th framework programme (2007-2010)

////////// Funding amounts, success rates, temporal trends & comparisons between
//////////////////////////////////// countries

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This study was conducted by the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity (FRB) according to one of the objectives of the Foundation which is to analyse information on biodiversity research actors, networks, funding sources, etc., and to its role as a member of the National contact point for the FP7 "Environment" theme (see the web site www.pcn-environnement.fr). The FRB is in charge of the sub-themes "Biodiversity", "Natural resources", and "Marine environments".

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FOREWORD

At the European level, biodiversity research projects can be funded by a range of tools: LIFE+, the Seventh Framework programme for research and development (FP7), the European regional development fund, the European agricultural fund for rural development, or ERA-nets such as the ERA-net BiodivERsA that now funds European research projects through annual calls for 6-10 M€ per year. Among those instruments, the “Environment” theme of the FP7 is recognized as a major source of funding. Indeed, the European Commission provides important funding support for a range of research projects encompassing several sub-activities, including biodiversity, as part of the FP7 “Environment” theme (Box 1).

Biodiversity, a cross-disciplinary topic, not identified as such in the FP7 “Environment” theme

Within the FP7, biodiversity crosses the boards and appears in various sub-activities: “Pressures on environment & climate”, “Marine environments”, “Sustainable management of resources”..., but there is not a unique and delimited entrance to fund biodiversity. Consequently, assessing the results of FP7 funding for the biodiversity research community and for the associated issues is complex.

To overcome this difficulty, the FRB (Box 2) conducted the present study based on the results of the projects submitted to the FP7. The main goal of the study is to assess the importance of biodiversity among the FP7 “Environment” theme in comparison with the identified sub-activities. Temporal trends of fundings are also assessed for the 2007-2010 period, and the relative performances of the participating countries are compared.

The FRB, member of the National Contact Point (NCP) for “environment” within the European NCP network

In order to facilitate the communication between the European Commission and the project managers for the

Framework Programs, National Contact Points (NCPs) were set up for each participating country. The NCPs are consortia gathering several kinds of expert bodies (public institutions, research institutes, universities, agencies, actors from the private sector, associations, etc.).

The main missions of NCPs are to:

- ▶ **inform** the potential participants to the European programmes about the EU funding opportunities in line with their projects and about the specificities of the topic they deal with;
- ▶ **back up each step of the projects** (from submission to negotiation) to improve the quality of the proposals and communicate on the current calls for proposals;
- ▶ **provide feedback** to the European Commission about suggestions or theme propositions for the elaboration of the annual FP work programmes.

In France, the NCPs network is headed by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research, particularly the Office for European affairs of the DGRI (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation). The NCP for the FP7 “Environment” theme is made up of four members, each one providing expertise on a specific field:

- ▶ ADEME (French Environment and Energy Management Agency), which coordinates the consortium, is in charge of the “Environmental technologies” subject;
- ▶ FRB is in charge of the “Sustainable management of resources”, “Marine environments” and “Biodiversity” subjects;
- ▶ INSU (National Institute for Earth Sciences and Astronomy) from the CNRS, is in charge of the “Earth observation”, “Environment and health”, “Natural hazards”, and “Assessment tools for sustainable development” subjects; and
- ▶ the association Enviropea is in charge of information management and communication.

Each year, the European Commission provides the results of the calls for proposals to the Member States, and NCPs can participate in the analysis of the results.

The FRB’s willingness to analyse the funding of the “biodiversity” topic within the FP7 “Environment” theme

The FRB performed this study as part of the missions it has been assigned and its role in the biodiversity subject in the Environment NCP. The main goals are to:

- ▶ **identify**, among the projects submitted or funded within the FP7, those dealing in part or entirely with biodiversity;
- ▶ **underline** the level of biodiversity funding within the theme “Environment” of the FP7, concerning the funding amounts, success rates of the submitted projects, etc., in comparison with figures obtained for the identified sub-activities of the FP7;
- ▶ **analyze** the temporal trends of funding and success rates for the period 2007-2010;

- ▶ **benchmark** the results of the different countries, analyzing more particularly the results for France.

We hope that the findings will be of interest to the researchers, institutes, stakeholders, policy makers and European Commission officers concerned with biodiversity. We expect that these results will help all of us to better consider the place of biodiversity, today and tomorrow, within the FP.

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Paris, 30 November 2011

Some more information about the mean size of funded projects, the results of countries not presented within this report etc., can be found at www.fondationbiodiversite.fr/le-financement-recherche/7eme-pcrdt

BOX 1

GENERAL PRESENTATION OF THE FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES

FIGURE A

EVOLUTION OF THE FP7 ANNUAL BUDGET

The Framework Programmes (FP) are funding tools for the European Union’s research. They gather almost all the funding sources for research in EU. The Seventh FP, lasting 7 years, covers the 2007-2013 period (fig.A). It comes with a 50 521 M€ budget (not including the “nuclear activities” topic), resulting as the most important funding programme for research in the world. The 7th FP is in line with the Lisbon Strategy for EU to become the “most dynamic and competitive knowledge-based economy in the world” and with the Barcelona Strategy, for which, the EU committed to raise the expenditure for research up to 3% of the GDP. The FP7 constitutes a key instrument to carry out these strategies. With this programme, the European Commission objective is to reinforce the scientific and technologic excellence and the competitiveness of the European Union. As a consequence, the annual budget for the FP7 has been doubled compared with the FP6.

FIGURE B

DISTRIBUTION OF THE FP7 AVERAGE ANNUAL BUDGET FOR THE 2007-2013 PERIOD (7217 M€) AMONG SPECIFIC PROGRAMMES

In addition to the Joint Research Center (JRC), the FP7 includes four specific programmes (fig. B):

- **Cooperation** (the main programme): It fosters collaborative research across Europe and other partner countries with transnational consortia of industry and academia, working on key thematic areas.
- **Ideas**: this programme, settled by the European Research Council, supports “frontier research” solely on the basis of scientific excellence, in any area of science and technology.
- **People**: this programme provides support for researcher mobility and career development, both for researchers inside the European Union and internationally.
- **Capacities**: the programme strengthens the research and innovation capacities throughout Europe and ensures their optimum use.

FIGURE C

DISTRIBUTION OF THE AVERAGE BUDGET OF THE FP7 COOPERATION PROGRAMME AMONG THE DIFFERENT THEMES (+ : estimated source of funding for biodiversity)

and biotechnology” theme. The present report focuses on the “Environment” theme, but also includes joint calls between the “Environment” theme and other themes.

THE FRENCH FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH ON BIODIVERSITY

The FRB, a French foundation for scientific cooperation and a science-society platform

The FRB was created in February 2008 by 8 major national research institutions, with support from the Ministries of Research and Environment. The FRB is composed of a governing board, a scientific committee and a stakeholder committee (over 110 stakeholders, including CSOs, private companies, managers of protected areas, managers of biological or genetic resources, and local authorities). About 30 FRB staff members implement the planned activities.

FRB financial resources are provided by its founding members¹ and the Ministry of Research according to recurrent funding. The Ministry of Environment, a range of firms, national agencies and the European commission support specific FRB projects. In 2010 and 2011, the annual funding amount for FRB was above 4 M€.

FRB's core mission is to promote French research on biodiversity and to enhance its coordination at the national, European and international levels as well as to support the dissemination of research outcomes towards stakeholders and end-users. The FRB also analyses information on biodiversity research actors, networks, funding sources, etc. The FRB is involved in the preparation and management of several national biodiversity programmes. The FRB also promotes the cooperation between science, civil society and business organizations and encourages innovation and mobilisation of expertise in the fields of biology, ecology, chemistry, socio-economics, legal sciences, etc.

See www.fondationbiodiversite.fr

The FRB, participant of several European and international projects to further support biodiversity research and its integration at an international level

* **BiodivERsA.** Part of the ERA-net scheme – which aims at making a reality of the European Research Area by encouraging collaborative research projects across Europe – the BiodivERsA initiative's goal is to build a sustainable platform for high-level biodiversity research on a transnational scale. In its second four-year phase since November 2010 and funded under the FP7, BiodivERsA works with a network of 21 national funding agencies in 15 countries to provide the funds, focus, and networking opportunities for biodiversity researchers to work efficiently on projects that help understand biodiversity dynamics, and to explore innovative solutions for the use, conservation and sustainable management of biological resources. A key objective

of BiodivERsA is to foster strategic cooperation among those working in biodiversity research and related disciplines, an ambition being supported by the organisation's own funding of pan-European research projects. In 2008, BiodivERsA launched its first European call on biodiversity, through which 12 international research projects have been selected and supported for a total funding of 14.2 M€. Following this first initiative, BiodivERsA now launches joint calls every year. The calls of November 2010 and November 2011, respectively focused on “biodiversity and ecosystem services and their valuation” and on “biodiversity dynamics: scenarios, resilience and tipping points” have a total budget of 8 M€ each one. FRB is the coordinator of BiodivERsA. See www.biodiversa.org

* **Biodiversity Knowledge** is a Coordination Action Project funded under the European Commission's FP7 since late 2010. The objective of the project is to develop a recommended design for a scientific biodiversity Network of Knowledge to inform policy-makers and other societal actors. This network will develop links to relevant clients to support the science-policy interface in Europe and beyond. The FRB is participating, as a task leader, in this project. See www.biodiversityknowledge.eu

* **BioVel** is a FP7 “Infrastructures” project that was launched in September 2011 and aims at developing a biodiversity e-laboratory for the scientific community, offering new tools for powerful analysis of large biodiversity datasets and for improving and sharing of workflows among experts. Close user involvement and close support and guidance are keys for the uptake of the tools and their continued success. The FRB is leading one of the workpackages of this project. See www.biovel.eu

* **CESAB.** The Centre for Synthesis and Analysis on Biodiversity, is a research centre where biodiversity experts are invited to share their data and concepts to develop meta-analyses and syntheses without producing new primary data. Experts from all nationalities have access to the resources and infrastructures needed to conduct such activities and address major scientific issues in the field of biodiversity. The FRB launched and keeps developing this centre located in Aix-en-Provence (France). See www.cesab.org

* **DIVERSITAS** is an international programme of biodiversity science, part of ICSU, with a dual mission: to promote an integrative biodiversity science, linking biological, ecological and social disciplines in an effort to produce socially relevant new knowledge, and to provide the scientific basis for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. In particular, DIVERSITAS fosters an integrated network of the world's leading biodiversity scientists to address critical biodiversity issues. The FRB is the French committee of DIVERSITAS, promoting links between experts and activities at the national and international levels. See www.diversitas-international.org/

1. The founding members of the FRB: BRGM (Bureau des recherches géologiques et minières), CEMAGREF (Centre national du machinisme agricole, du génie rural, des eaux et forêt), CIRAD (Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement), CNRS (Centre national de la recherche scientifique), IFREMER (Institut français de recherche pour l'exploitation de la mer), INRA (Institut national de la recherche agronomique), IRD (Institut de recherche pour le développement), MNHN (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle).

A] METHODS USED

A.1 INFORMATION SOURCES AND VOCABULARY USED

The information used to carry out this study is produced by the European Commission for the Member States. It deals with the results of the calls for proposals of the FP7 “Environment” theme (years 2007 to 2010) and is extracted from the E-Corda database. The financial amounts of the projects indicated in the study as “funding amounts” correspond to the financial contributions required by the teams of the project. Consequently, for the funded projects, this corresponds to the amounts required

before the negotiation with the European Commission. It was not possible to take into account the funding data determined after the negotiation. Indeed, the distribution of budget among participants was available to the FRB only for requested funding and not for actual funding. Although slight variations might appear in comparison with the final grants given, the difference is small (an average of -2% for the biodiversity projects).

The vocabulary used in the report is consistent with the one used for European Commission activities, and is detailed in [appendix 1](#).

BOX 3

LIST OF THE FP7 “ENVIRONMENT” THEME CALLS FOR PROPOSALS TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT

2007

FP7-ENV-2007-1: Environment main call
FP7-ERANET-2007-RTD: Era-net call
FP7-Adhoc-2007-13

2008

FP7-ENV-2008-1: Environment main call
FP7-ENV-NMP-2008-2: Cross-thematic cooperation between Environment and Nanosciences, nanotechnologies, materials and new production technologies (NMP)

2009

FP7-ENV-2009-1: Environment main call
FP7-2009-BIOREFINERY: Cross-thematic cooperation between Agriculture and Fisheries, and Biotechnology (KBBE), Nanosciences, nanotechnologies, materials and new production technologies (NMP), Energy, Environment
FP7-ERANET-2009-RTD: Era-net call
FP7-NMP-ENV-2009: Cross-thematic cooperation between Environment and Nanosciences, nanotechnologies, materials and new production technologies (NMP)

2010

FP7-ENV-2010: Environment main call
FP7-OCEAN-2010: “The ocean of tomorrow” call, joint call between the Themes Food, Agriculture and Fisheries, and Biotechnology (KBBE), Energy, Environment (including Climate Change), Transport (including Aeronautics), Socio-economic Sciences and Humanities
FP7-2010-GC-ELECTROCHEMICAL-STORAGE: Public-Private Partnership call “Green Cars”, cross-thematic cooperation between NMP, Energy, Environment (including Climate Change), Transport (including Aeronautics)
FP7-2010-NMP-ENV-ENERGY-ICT-EeB: Public-Private Partnership “Energy-efficient Buildings”, cross thematic cooperation between Nanosciences, nanotechnologies, materials and new production technologies (NMP), Information and communication technologies (ICT), Energy, Environment (including climate change)
FP7-AFRICA-2010: Call for AFRICA, cross-thematic cooperation between Health, Food, Agriculture and fisheries, and Biotechnology, and Environment
FP7-ERANET-2010-RTD: Era-net call

A.2 LIST OF THE CALLS FOR PROPOSALS TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT

The projects funded within the “Cooperation” programme are selected through calls for proposals, issued annually by the European Commission. Every year, a work programme is published, announcing the topics covered by the funding in each sub-activity of each theme.

Several calls for proposals may be issued at the same time the same year: one main call (general Environment call) goes along with one or several specific calls (i.e.: cross-thematic joint calls with other themes of the Cooperation programme). The year of the work programme corresponding to the call is named “year of call”.

FIGURE 1

SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE APPROACH USED

Information on submitted and funded projects within the FP7 is provided according to the pre-defined sub-activities of the “Environment” theme, which allows analyses of funding and success rates for these sub-activities. Among these projects, we also identified biodiversity projects (i.e. addressing fully or partly a biodiversity issue), which allowed analysis for a “virtual” biodiversity sub-activity within the FP7.

All the calls published within the Environment programme (main and specific calls) were taken into account in this study (Box 3). For the cross-thematic calls between several themes (ex: Environment and NMP), the projects depend on one or the other theme of the call, receiving funds from this theme. In this case, only the projects of the joint call attached to the Environment theme were taken into account.

A.3 IDENTIFICATION OF BIODIVERSITY PROJECTS

In order to analyze the results for biodiversity subject, it is first necessary to select the relevant projects (Fig 1). There is no specific entrance for this subject within the Environment programme. As biodiversity is a cross-field subject it is possible to find it in any sub-activity of the Environment programme. Biodiversity is defined here according to the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity: “Biological diversity” means the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.

The authors selected the projects dealing in part or entirely with biodiversity, on the basis of the data from the European Commission: we used the title and the summary of the projects, and also the summary of project reviews when needed. Indeed, as member of the National Contact Point consortium, the FRB receives the evaluation results of the projects submitted to the FP (quick call information). The projects were screened as follows:

- ▶ we identified all the projects submitted to calls dealing partly or entirely with biodiversity;
- ▶ we also screened all the 1626 submitted projects using the following keywords in their title or abstract, whatever the call: biodiversity, biological diversity, species, genetic diversity, genetic resource(s), natural resource(s), biosphere, ecological service(s), environmental service(s), or ecosystem service(s);
- ▶ we read and assessed whether biodiversity represented a significant part of those projects;
- ▶ when needed, we took the Evaluation Summary Report into account.

The list of the biodiversity funded projects identified is provided in appendix 2.

B] BIODIVERSITY WITHIN THE FP7 “ENVIRONMENT” THEME: IMPORTANCE AND TEMPORAL TRENDS

Biodiversity represents an important part of the “Environment” theme of the FP7, i.e. 20% of funding for the period 2007-2010, for a corresponding amount of 171 M€. Among the 1626 projects submitted to the “Environment” theme over this period, 275 projects were relevant to the biodiversity subject (appendix 3). Among the 275 projects funded among all the sub-activities of the “Environment” theme, 44 funded projects were relevant to the biodiversity subject (appendix 3).

annual value ranging from 200 to 220 M€. In contrast, the part of the budget allocated to projects addressing at least partly one or several biodiversity issue(s) has significantly decreased between 2007 and 2010, from 23.6% in 2007 to 17.9% in 2010.

It is important to remember that the figures of actual funding of biodiversity research activities are lower than the ones given above, since many projects only partly address biodiversity issues. For instance, a given project on adaptation to climate change can have only one third of its funding devoted to biodiversity research. This level of information would have been useful, but access to this information was not available. Thus, in this study, “biodiversity projects” and “biodiversity funding” correspond to “projects/funding of projects dealing in part or entirely with biodiversity”.

B.1 TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF THE ANNUAL FUNDING FOR BIODIVERSITY AS COMPARED TO THE WHOLE “ENVIRONMENT” THEME

The funding amount allocated to the “Environment” theme has been roughly constant since 2007 (Fig 2), with an

FIGURE 2

TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF THE BUDGET FOR THE FP7 “ENVIRONMENT” THEME AND OF THE PERCENTAGE DEDICATED TO BIODIVERSITY

Temporal changes in (green bars) the total annual funding* allocated to the FP7 “Environment” theme, and (blue squares) the part of that funding allocated to biodiversity projects. The overall budget has not significantly (NS) changed, whereas the fraction devoted to biodiversity has significantly decreased.

* Here and in all graphs hereafter, amount of funding refers to grant requested before negotiations.

FIGURE 3

TEMPORAL VARIATION IN THE NUMBER OF PROJECTS

Temporal variation in the number of projects, either evaluated or funded, and in the success rate of evaluated projects, for (upper panel) projects of the whole “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects.

B.2 TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF THE NUMBER OF SUBMITTED PROJECTS AND SUCCESS RATE

The success rate of the projects submitted within the “Environment” theme of the FP7, based on the ratio of funded to evaluated projects, has increased between 2007 and 2010 (Fig 3). The weak success rate in 2007 and to a lower extent 2008 was due to a particularly large initial participation when the FP7 was launched. The next years, possibly due to this low initial success rate, the number of submitted projects declined, leading to a higher average success rate (more than 20% since 2009).

The success rate of the biodiversity projects (16%) is a bit lower than the average value computed for all the projects from the “Environment” theme (16.9%), with a particularly low value observed in 2007 due to a huge number of submitted proposals. The number and type of funded biodiversity projects slightly changed over the years. Indeed, there have been fewer projects in 2008, but with a bigger size, followed by an increase in the number of funded projects in 2009 and to a lesser extent 2010. However, this evolution should not hide the downward trend observed for funding allocated to biodiversity since 2007.

C] WHICH SUB-ACTIVITIES OF THE FP7 “ENVIRONMENT” THEME FUND BIODIVERSITY PROJECTS?

C.1 DISTRIBUTION OF FUNDING AMOUNTS AMONG SUB-ACTIVITIES

The “Environment” theme is divided into 11 sub-activities. Over the 2007-2010 period, the most important sub-activities in terms of funding were “Environmental technologies” and “Pressure on environment and climate” (Fig 4). Among the “Environment” theme, there is no specific sub-activity for biodiversity. Indeed, biodiversity is considered as a cross-field subject, shared among several

sub-activities. According to our study, we concluded that, on average over the 2007-2010 period, biodiversity projects represented 20% of the total funding within the “Environment” theme. Biodiversity has mainly been financed by the sub-activities “Sustainable management of resources” (38.8% of this sub-activity) and “Marine environment” (34.9%) (Fig 4). The sub-activity “Pressure on environment and climate” also funded a substantial part of the biodiversity projects (13.2%). Similar results are obtained when focusing on funding of French participants (Box 4).

FIGURE 4

DISTRIBUTION OF FUNDING AMOUNTS CUMULATED OVER THE 2007-2010 PERIOD

BOX 4

FOCUS ON FRENCH RESULTS: DISTRIBUTION OF FUNDING AMOUNTS AMONG SUB-ACTIVITIES

Over the 2007-2010 period, France has received a total funding amount of 66 M€ from the "Environment" theme, from which 15 M€ were allocated to biodiversity projects. This amount

represents 8.8% of the biodiversity amount of funding for biodiversity for all the countries.

For the whole "Environment" theme, over a quarter of the budget received by France came from the "Pressures on environment and climate" sub-activity, whereas the four other main sub-activities in terms of funding were "Environmental technologies", "Earth observation", "Sustainable management of natural resources" and "Marine environments".

The funding of French participants in biodiversity projects represented about 22.8% of the total budget distributed to France. The sub-activity "Sustainable management of resources" funded the majority of the biodiversity projects (39.6%). Two other sub-activities significantly contributed to funding of biodiversity projects: "Marine Environments" (33%) and "Pressures on climate change" (20.3%).

FIGURE 5

AVERAGE FUNDING AMOUNT REQUESTED AND SUCCESS RATES BY SUB-ACTIVITIES

Average funding amount requested by submitted (evaluated) and funded projects over the 2007-2010 period, along with corresponding success rate, by sub-activity, for (upper panel) projects of the whole “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The additional panel at the bottom-right presents the aggregated results for all biodiversity projects.

At the “Environment” theme level, the success rates were highly variable, ranging from 11.7% to 33.1% from a sub-activity to another (Fig 5, top). This was mainly due to the variable number of projects submitted and thus the funding requested in some sub-activities with regard to the budget allocated, leading to variable competition rates. The sub-activity “Sustainable management of resources” received many submissions, leading to the lowest success rate. On the contrary, the theme “Marine Environments” and “Earth observation” had the lowest competition rate.

Within the sub-activity “Sustainable management of resources”, among the 122 M€ of funding available, 66 M€

were allocated to biodiversity projects (i.e. 53.4%) (Fig 5, bottom). For “Marine environments”, 60 M€ among the 89 M€ available, i.e. 66.9%, were allocated to biodiversity projects.

Considering all the biodiversity projects (Fig 5, bottom-right), the success rate observed was 18%, which is a bit lower than the values observed for most of the pre-defined sub-activities. This is mainly due to the large number of projects submitted by the biodiversity

research community. It is interesting to note that a similar conclusion can be made:

- at the European level, accounting for the results of the calls for proposals launched by the ERA-net BiodivERsA: the 2008 open call and the 2010 targeted call of BiodivERsA lead to success rates of 7.3% and 13.2%, respectively. In both cases, this was due to the high number of submitted projects;

- at a national scale in France: a huge number of biodiversity projects have been submitted to the “biodiversity” calls for proposals of ANR in 2005, 2006 and 2007 for instance, and success the rate was around 10% in 2005.

This suggests that the size of the biodiversity community research might often be underestimated by funders.

FIGURE 6

TEMPORAL VARIATION OF THE YEARLY AMOUNT OF FUNDING ALLOCATED BY SUB-ACTIVITIES

Temporal variation over the 2007-2010 period of the yearly amount of funding allocated among sub-activities for (upper panel) all projects of the “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The additional panel at the bottom-right presents the aggregated results for all biodiversity projects.

C.2 TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF THE IMPORTANCE OF BIODIVERSITY FUNDING AMONG SUB-ACTIVITIES OF THE “ENVIRONMENT” THEME

For the sub-activities that have been the main sources of funding for biodiversity in the “Environment” theme (i.e. “Pressures on environment and climate”, “Sustainable management of resources” and “marine environments”), different trends are observed for the total amount of funding and for the amount of funding for biodiversity projects distributed through these sub-activities.

Total funding through the “Pressures on environment and climate” sub-activity remained constant over the 2007-2009 period and was lower in 2010 (Fig 6 top), while no clear temporal trend was observed for biodiversity funding within this sub-activity (Fig 6 bottom). For the “Sustainable management of resources” sub-activity, the funding allocated to biodiversity projects increased concurrently to the raise in the total funding. Most of the funding available for that sub-activity was allocated to biodiversity projects.

In contrast, although the total budget for the “Marine environments” sub-activity remained stable, the part of this funding allocated to biodiversity projects was much lower in 2009-2010 than in 2007-2008. The projects on marine biodiversity may have access to new funding opportunities outside the “Environment” theme of FP7, which should be investigated.

Overall, the “Marine environments” sub-activity was the major source of funding for biodiversity in 2007-2008, whereas the “Sustainable management of resources” sub-activity was the major source (although not exclusive) since 2009.

DJ COMPARATIVE ANALYSES OF RESULTS BETWEEN COUNTRIES

FIGURE 7

RANKING OF COUNTRIES ACCORDING TO THE NUMBER OF COORDINATIONS

D.1 ANALYSIS OF PROJECT COORDINATION

Considering all the funded projects of the “Environment” theme over the 2007-2010 period, Germany had the highest number (51) of coordinations (Fig 7 top), followed by the United Kingdom, The Netherlands and Italy (39, 37 and 28 coordinations, respectively). France had the 5th position with 20 coordinated projects.

In regard to biodiversity projects (Fig 7 bottom), the United Kingdom coordinated the highest (12) number of projects. Germany, France, and Norway were the other most successful countries, with respectively 8, 5 and 4 coordinated projects. The United Kingdom and France had particularly good results in terms of coordination of biodiversity projects, in comparison to coordination numbers for the general “Environment” theme. Actually, around 25% of the projects coordinated by France or by the United Kingdom dealt with biodiversity. However these figures concern the whole 2007-2010 period and sometimes do not reflect important temporal variations.

Ranking of countries according to the number of funded projects that they coordinated over the 2007-2010 period for (upper panel) all projects of the “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The first 15 countries are presented in the upper panel whereas all the countries coordinating at least one biodiversity project are presented in the lower one.

FIGURE 8

TEMPORAL VARIATION OF THE NUMBER OF COORDINATIONS

Temporal variation of the number of funded projects that each country coordinated during the 2007-2010 period for (upper panel) all projects of the “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The first 15 countries are presented in the upper panel whereas all the countries coordinating at least one biodiversity project are presented in the lower panel.

Focusing on the temporal evolution of the number of coordinations within the whole “Environment” theme, no clear temporal trend is observed over the 2007-2010 period for Germany, the United Kingdom and Italy (Fig 8 top). In contrast, a linear increase in the coordination number is observed for The Netherlands whereas the coordination number for France was higher in 2007 than for the 2008-2010 period.

Considering biodiversity projects only, and keeping in mind that observed trends can be viewed with caution due to the low numbers considered, the United Kingdom

and to a lesser extent Germany had variable results over time (for the United Kingdom: 5 coordinations in 2007 and in 2009, not any in 2010). Among the most striking features, the number of Dutch coordinations of biodiversity projects remained very low, and even null in 2010, despite the marked increase in the total number of Dutch coordinations. In contrast, the number of French coordinations of biodiversity projects remained stable, and even higher in 2010, despite the decrease in the total number of French coordinations. This highlights the increased relative importance of biodiversity in terms of French coordinations within the “Environment” theme.

FIGURE 9

RANKING OF COUNTRIES ACCORDING TO THE FUNDING ALLOCATED

Ranking of countries according to the cumulated funding allocated to national participants of each country over the 2007-2010 period for (upper panel) all projects of the “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The first 15 countries are presented in each panel.

D.2 ANALYSIS OF FUNDING ALLOCATED

In the “Environment” theme, Germany and the United Kingdom lead the grant ranking, with 121 M€ and 117 M€ respectively (Fig 9 top). They were followed by The Netherlands (86 M€), France (66 M€, 4th place) and Italy (65 M€).

The ranking of countries is different for the funding amount for biodiversity projects (Fig 9 bottom). The United Kingdom has been allocated the highest amount (31 M€), followed by Germany (20 M€), France (15 M€), Norway and The Netherlands (14 M€ each). In the field of biodiversity, the United Kingdom, France and Norway obtained relatively better results than in the general “Environment” theme. However, temporal trends are also important to consider here.

FIGURE 10

TEMPORAL VARIATION OF THE FUNDING ALLOCATED, BY COUNTRIES

Temporal variation of the funding allocated to national participants of each country during the 2007-2010 period for (upper panel) all projects of the “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The first 15 countries are presented.

At the “Environment” theme level, no clear trend can be observed for the temporal evolution of total funding for most countries (Fig 10 top), with a slight tendency to increase for the United Kingdom, The Netherlands and Spain. The annual total amount allocated to French teams was higher in 2007 than in the 2008-2010 period.

For a given country, very different trends can be observed for the funding of biodiversity (Fig 10 bottom). For instance, funding amount has continuously decreased for the United Kingdom since 2007, whereas no obvious trend can be observed for Germany, France, The Netherlands or Spain.

FIGURE 11

RANKING OF COUNTRIES ACCORDING TO THE NUMBER OF PRESENCES

Ranking of countries according to the number of presences for each country in funded projects over the 2007-2010 period for (upper panel) all projects of the "Environment" theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The first 15 countries are presented.

D.3 ANALYSIS OF THE NUMBER OF PRESENCES OF NATIONAL TEAMS IN FUNDED PROJECTS

Country ranking according to the number of presences of national teams in funded projects (Fig 11 top) was close to that obtained for funding, with Germany (present in 76% of the projects) and the United Kingdom (71.6%) having the highest number of presences. These two countries were followed by France, The Netherlands, Italy and Spain, which were present in 57.1 to 51.3% of the funded projects.

When considering the number of presences for biodiversity projects (Fig 11 bottom), the United Kingdom was present in 88.6% of the biodiversity projects. Germany, Spain and France were respectively present in 79.5%, 68.2% and 65.9% of the projects. Again, it is worth considering the temporal trends that can strongly differ between countries

FIGURE 12

TEMPORAL VARIATION OF THE NUMBER OF PRESENCES, BY COUNTRIES

Temporal variation of the number of presences for each country in funded projects during the 2007-2010 period for (upper panel) all projects of the “Environment” theme and (lower panel) biodiversity projects. The first 15 countries are presented.

The number of presences in projects of the “Environment” theme (Fig 12 top) has decreased over the 2007-2010 period for France and Germany. No clear trend was observed for the United Kingdom, The Netherlands, and Italy. In contrast, the number of presences has slightly increased for Spain and Belgium.

For biodiversity projects, the temporal trends are often quite different. For instance, no clear trend was observed for Germany, France or The Netherlands. Concurrently, a decreasing trend was observed for Norway (Fig 12 bottom).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Our results mainly show that:

- ▶ The total amount of funding for research projects in the whole “Environment” theme of FP7 remained roughly constant over the 2007-2010 while the fraction of that funding allocated to biodiversity projects declined from 23.6% to 17.9%.
- ▶ Within the “Environment” theme, biodiversity projects were mainly funded through three sub-activities during the 2007-2010 period:
 - “sustainable management of resources” (38.8%);
 - “marine environments” (34.9%);
 - “pressure on environment and climate” (13.2%).

However, the sub-activities which were the main sources of funding for biodiversity noticeably changed over time: the “Marine environments” sub-activity was the major source of funding for biodiversity in 2007-2008, whereas the “sustainable management of resources” sub-activity has become the major source of funding and a more clearly identified one (although not exclusive) for biodiversity in 2009-2010. This trend is consistent with the fact that biodiversity is an increasingly accounted for issue in the sustainable management of biological resources by the European Commission.

- ▶ The mean success rate observed for biodiversity projects was around 18% in terms of funding, which was a bit lower than the mean values observed for most of the pre-defined sub-activities. This was mainly due to the large number of submitted projects that related (or at least partly related) to biodiversity topics. Due to a high number of projects submitted, similar low success rates for biodiversity projects are also observed in other European (e.g. BiodivERSA) and national (e.g. ANR in France) calls for proposals focusing on biodiversity. This suggests that the size of the biodiversity community research and the

associated number of projects that it can submit to adequate calls for proposals are substantial. Such a strong capacity of the biodiversity community may often be ignored and/or underestimated by funders.

- ▶ Considering the whole “Environment” theme, Germany, the United Kingdom and The Netherlands were the three countries being allocated the highest amounts of funding, followed by France and Italy. The ranking of countries was different for the funding amount allocated to biodiversity projects: the main countries were (in decreasing order) the United Kingdom, Germany, France, Norway and The Netherlands. The United Kingdom, France and Norway obtained relatively better mean results for biodiversity than the general “Environment” theme over the 2007-2010 period.
- ▶ When considering the whole “Environment” theme, no clear temporal trend was observed for the evolution of total funding for most countries over the 2007-2010 period. When considering only biodiversity projects, funding amount decreased for the United Kingdom, whereas no clear trend was observed for Germany, France, The Netherlands or Spain.

In April 2009, the President of the European Commission José Manuel Durão Barroso stated that *“The loss of biodiversity is a global threat that is just as important as global warming. It threatens our natural environment and thus, the quality of our life. But biodiversity underpins also our economies. It is not therefore only because of the love of nature or a vision for our environment that we should keep biodiversity on the political agenda.”* In October 2010, he declared that *“We are standing at a crossroads: either we take concerted action to reverse biodiversity loss as soon as possible, or we compromise our own future and that of generations not yet born. (...) Firstly, it is important that we adopt a new and effective strategic plan; one that encourages collective action and is supported by all those who use biodiversity and whose activities have an impact on it.”*

However, the actual part of the funding from the FP7 “Environment” theme devoted to research projects at least partly related to biodiversity (and which are expected to generate new knowledge useful to cope with major biodiversity issues) decreased from 2007 to 2010. This could be explained by the emergence or development of other sources of funding for biodiversity research elsewhere at a European level. But this decrease could also be due to a silent decrease of funding for biodiversity research, linked to a silent decrease of the importance of biodiversity in the political agendas.

Actually, biodiversity is increasingly viewed as a transversal issue, to be addressed mainly in relation with and through other sectoral issues and other associated

funding sources.¹ This peculiarity makes it difficult and time-consuming (as in the present study) to effectively assess the actual values and trends of biodiversity research funding. This peculiarity also makes it of paramount importance to better understand what these values and trends are, and what the associated general strategy to support biodiversity research is: this is needed for a critical evaluation of the way research funders cope with the grand challenge of our time that biodiversity represents.

1. In FP5, biodiversity and ecosystems were visible in their own right, whereas FP6 was the heyday of biodiversity, which shared a platform with climate change (DG Research created a biodiversity sector at that time). In FP7, biodiversity became the last word for a sub-theme and the biodiversity sector was suppressed. We now see that biodiversity issues exclusively appear in the section “Sustainably managing natural resources and ecosystems” in preparatory documents for FP8, while the word biodiversity has vanished from sub-challenge title.

APPENDICES

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APPENDIX 1

GLOSSARY, COUNTRY TYPOLOGY and DOCUMENTS USED

GLOSSARY:

Average financial size: The average financial size of the projects (for instance for a sub-activity) equals the total funding amounts requested in the different projects divided by the number of projects.

Coordinator and members of a consortium: In most of the FP7 programmes, the candidates are asked to form consortia gathering a coordinator, key contact of the European Commission (during the negotiation step, and to a large extent throughout the lifetime of the project) and of the participants.

There is always one and unique coordination per project. The coordinator is the participant in charge of the administrative and financial management of the project. In practice, it is often the organisation the coordinator is related to, that plays this role (*Source: ANRT*).

Evaluated project: all the eligible projects that have been assessed during the evaluation process are evaluated projects, no matter if, eventually, they have been retained for funding or not.

The experts will assess a project when found eligible, that is to say a project complying with the following criteria:

- ▶ Deadline for application
- ▶ Minimum number of eligible, independent partners
- ▶ Completeness of proposal
- ▶ Presence of all requested documents (Parts A & B)
- ▶ Proposal in scope of the call (*Source: MESR/ANRT*).

Financial contributions requested in the projects:

Each participant asks for a financial support to the European Commission for its participation. The total sum corresponds to the addition of the individual participations.

For example, if 3 French institutes participating to a project request 1 000 000 € for each, it means that France asks for 3 000 000 € in this project (*Source: MESR/ANRT*).

Financial tools: the financial tools or funding schemes are detailed for each open topic and correspond

to the kind of expected project for this topic. In the “Environment” theme, there are 4 main funding schemes:

- ▶ Large scale collaborative project (between 4 and 8 M€ per project in average)
- ▶ Small/medium scale collaborative projects (maximum 3,5 M€)
- ▶ Coordination Action (maximum 2 M€)
- ▶ Support Action (maximum 2 M€)

Participation: A participation is registered each time an organisation, under the legal personality status, formally apply to a FP7 call for proposals, for an individual action or, the most frequently, within a multipartner project. The participation number of a country corresponds to the number of teams coming from this country and present in this project. For example, if two French teams participate to the same project, two participations will be registered for France (*Source: ANRT*).

Presence: A country (or other geographical scale), an organisation, or a grouping of organisations is considered as present in a project as soon as it is represented once. That is to say, when at least one of its team participates to the project. Thus, if several teams of one country are present in a project, there will be only one presence counted for this country (*Source: ANRT*).

Selected project or funded project: a project chosen, retained for funding. The core evaluation criteria are:

- ▶ **QUALITY:** scientific and technical excellence of the project, methodology and work plan
- ▶ **IMPLEMENTATION:** quality of the management structure and procedures (experience, quality, complementarity and balance of the consortium and the individual participants, appropriateness of allocation of financial and staff resources)
- ▶ **IMPACT:** contribution to expected impacts, accurateness with the EU’s challenges and policies, dissemination/exploitation of project results

To be selected, the project shall obtain scores over the threshold for each one of the three criteria (threshold at 3/5). All the projects that have passed this threshold will be ranked in priority order, according to the scores.

One or several projects can be retained, depending on the topic requirements and the budget (those projects are listed on the rank list). A reserve list can also complete the rank list. Proposals on the reserve list can be eventually funded if an additional budget is made available. Then, the European Commission invites the coordinator to enter negotiations for a grant agreement on the proposal before the signature of the contract and the allocation of funding.

Success rate: the success rates express the ratio of the sum of the participations, presences or financial amounts of selected projects to the same sum for evaluated projects.

Themes and sub-activity: A programme is divided into several themes (ex: the Cooperation programme is divided into the themes Health, Food, Environment, etc.). Each one of those themes is then divided into several activities and sub-activities. For example, the “Environment” theme is divided into 4 activities, sub-divided into 11 sub-activities in total which are detailed below (Source: MESR).

Activities and sub-activities of the “Environment” theme:

▶ **Activity 6.1. Climate change, pollution and risks**

— **Sub-activity 6.1.1. Pressures on the environment and climate:** functioning of climate and the earth and marine system including the polar regions; adaptation and mitigation measures; pollution in air, soil and water; changes in atmospheric composition and water cycle; global and regional interactions between climate and atmosphere, land surface, ice and the ocean; and impacts on biodiversity and ecosystems, including the effects of the sea level rise on coastal zones and impacts on particularly sensitive areas.

— **Sub-activity 6.1.2. Environment and health:** interaction of environmental stressors with human health including identification of sources, biomonitoring research for environment related health, indoor air quality and links to indoor environment, urban environment, car emissions and impact and emerging risk factors; integrated risk methods for hazardous substances including alternatives to animal testing; quantification and cost-benefit analysis of environmental health risks and indicators for prevention strategies.

— **Sub-activity 6.1.3. Natural hazards:** improvement of forecasting and integrated hazards – vulnerability – and risk assessments for disasters related to geological hazards (such as earthquakes, volcanoes, tsunamis) and climate (such as storms, droughts,

floods, forest fires, landslides, avalanches and other extreme events) and their impact; development of early warning systems and improve prevention, mitigation and management strategies, also within a multi-risk approach.

▶ **Activity 6.2. Sustainable Management of Resources**

— **Sub-activity 6.2.1. Conservation and sustainable management of natural and man-made resources and biodiversity:** ecosystems; water resources management; waste management and prevention; protection and management of biodiversity, including control of invasive alien species, soil, seabed, lagoons and coastal areas protection, approaches against desertification and land degradation, preservation of landscape; sustainable use and management of forests; sustainable management and planning of urban environment, including postindustrialized zones; data management and information services; assessment and foresight relating to natural processes.

— **Sub-activity 6.2.2. Management of marine environments:** impact of human activities on the marine environment and its resources; pollution and eutrophication in regional seas and coastal areas; deep sea ecosystems; assessment of marine biodiversity trends, of ecosystem processes and of ocean circulation; seabed geology; development of strategies, concepts and tools for a sustainable use of the ocean and its resources.

▶ **Activity 6.3. Environmental Technologies**

— **Sub-activity 6.3.1. Environmental technologies for observation, simulation, prevention, mitigation, adaptation, remediation and restoration of the natural and man-made environment:** related to water, climate, air, marine, urban and rural environment, soil, waste treatment, recycling, clean production processes and sustainable products, chemicals safety.

— **Sub-activity 6.3.2. Protection, conservation and enhancement of cultural heritage, including human habitat:** improved damage assessment on cultural heritage; development of innovative conservation strategies; fostering of the integration of cultural heritage in the urban setting.

— **Sub-activity 6.3.3. Technology assessment, verification and testing:** methods and tools for environmental risk and lifecycle assessment of processes, technologies and products, including alternative testing strategies and in particular non-

animal methods for industrial chemicals; support for sustainable chemistry, forest-based sector technology, water supply and sanitation platforms; scientific and technological aspects of a future European environmental technologies verification and testing programme, complementing third party assessment instruments.

▶ **Activity 6.4. Earth observation and assessment tools**

— **Sub-activity 6.4.1. Earth and ocean observation systems and monitoring methods for the environment and sustainable development:**

contribute to the development and integration of observation systems for environmental and sustainability issues in the framework of GEOSS (to which GMES is complementary); interoperability between systems and optimisation of information for understanding, modelling and predicating environmental phenomena, for assessing, exploring and managing natural resources.

— **Sub-activity 6.4.2. Forecasting methods and assessment tools for sustainable development taking into account differing scales of observation:**

modelling links between economy/environment/society including market based instruments, externalities, thresholds and developing the knowledge base and methodologies for sustainability impact assessment on key issues such as land use and marine issues; urban development, social and economic tensions related to climate change.

▶ **Activity 6.5. Horizontal actions**

— **Sub-activity 6.5.1. Dissemination and horizontal activities:**

strengthening the dissemination of Community research outcomes – also through the exploitation of synergies with complementary funding mechanisms at Community and Member State levels – and stimulating their uptake by relevant end-users, targeting in particular policymakers (*Source: European Commission*).

COUNTRY TYPOLOGY:

- ▶ **EU Member States:** UE-27
- ▶ **Candidate country:** Croatia – Macedonia – Turkey
- ▶ **Associated State:** an Associated State is a third country that has entered into an Association Agreement with the Community involving its financial contribution to the FP7.
List of the Associated States: Albania – Bosnia-Herzegovina – Iceland – Israel – Liechtenstein – Montenegro – Norway – Serbia – Switzerland
The Associated States and the Member States have to meet the same requirements in the FP7.
- ▶ **International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC):** is a third country classified as low income/medium-up income/medium-low income by the European Commission, and identified as such in the FP7 work programme.
- ▶ **Third country:** Non-member country, non-candidate and non-associated to the European Union.

DOCUMENTS USED:

- ▶ **Quick call information and full brick** for all the calls from 2007 to 2010 (data provided by the EC to the Member States and then the NCPs)
- ▶ **Statistics analysis** documents realized by the MESR-DGSIP-DGRI-SIES out of the EC's database E-Corda-FP7 proposals and participants database with:
 - indicators for the 16 main countries participating to the FP7 (16 March 2011)
 - FP7 indicators by geographical areas (16 mars 2011)
 - France (detailed by sub-activity) (26 oct 2010)

APPENDIX 2

LIST OF BIODIVERSITY PROJECTS THAT HAVE BEEN FUNDED

Projects in bold are coordinated by France, projects highlighted in blue include at least one French participant

TOPIC	ACRONYM	TITLE	COORDINATOR COUNTRY	FUNDING SCHEME
2007				
ENV.2007.1.1.3.1.	EPOCA	European Project on Ocean Acidification	FR	CP Large
ENV.2007.2.1.4.1.	SOILSERVICE	Conflicting demands of land use, soil biodiversity and the sustainable delivery of ecosystem goods and services in Europe	SE	CP small/medium
ENV.2007.2.1.4.2.	PALMS	Palm harvest impacts in tropical forests	DK	CP small/medium
ENV.2007.2.1.4.3.	HighARCS	Highland aquatic resources conservation and sustainable development	UK	CP small/medium
	HUNT	Hunting for sustainability	UK	CP small/medium
	LiveDiverse	Sustainable livelihoods and biodiversity in riparian areas in developing countries	SE	CP small/medium
ENV.2007.2.2.1.2.	EELIAD	European eels in the atlantic: assessment of their decline	UK	CP small/medium
	SALSEA-Merge	Advancing understanding of Atlantic salmon at sea: merging genetics and ecology to resolve stock-specific migration and distribution patterns	NO	CP small/medium
ENV.2007.2.2.1.3.	CoralFISH	Assessment of the interaction between corals, fish and fisheries, in order to develop monitoring and predictive modelling tools for ecosystem based management in the deep waters of Europe and beyond	IE	CP Large
ENV.2007.2.2.1.4.	MEECE	Marine ecosystem evolution in a changing environment	UK	CP Large
ENV.2007.2.2.1.6.	CAREX	Coordination action for research activities on life in extreme environments	UK	CSA
ENV.2007.3.3.1.1.	MIDTAL	Microarrays for the Detection of Toxic ALgae	DE*	CP small/medium
ENV.2007.4.1.1.2.	EBONE	European biodiversity observation network; a project to design and test a biodiversity observation system integrated in time and space	NL	CP small/medium
ENV.2007.4.2.1.1.	TESS	Transactional Environmental Support System	EL	CP small/medium
2008				
ENV.2008.1.1.5.2.	ATP	Arctic tipping points	NO	CP Large
ENV.2008.2.1.3.1.	PRACTICE	Prevention and Restoration Actions to Combat Desertification. An Integrated Assessment	ES	CSA
ENV.2008.2.1.4.1.	BioFresh	Biodiversity of freshwater ecosystems: Status, trends, pressures, and conservation priorities	DE	CP Large
ENV.2008.2.1.4.4.	SCALES	Securing the conservation of biodiversity across administrative levels and spatial, temporal, and ecological scales	DE	CP Large
ENV.2008.2.2.1.1.	MESMA	Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Areas	NL	CP Large
ENV.2008.2.2.1.2.	HERMIONE	Hotspot ecosystem research and Man's impact on European seas	UK	CP Large

TOPIC	ACRONYM	TITLE	COORDINATOR COUNTRY	FUNDING SCHEME
ENV.2008.2.2.1.3.	KnowSeas	Knowledge-based sustainable management for Europe's seas	UK	CP Large
ENV.2008.4.1.1.1.	EUROGEOSS	European approach to GEOSS	FR	CP Large
ENV.2008.5.1.0.1.	ComEnvir	Communicating environmental impacts on water quality, availability and use	DE	CSA
2009				
ENV.2009.1.1.6.2	RESPONSES	European responses to climate change: deep emissions reductions and mainstreaming of mitigation and adaptation	NL	CP small/medium
ENV.2009.2.1.2.1	REFRESH	Adaptive Strategies to Mitigate the Impacts of Climate Change on European Freshwater Ecosystems	UK	CP Large
ENV.2009.2.1.3.2	LEDDRA	Land and Ecosystem Degradation and Desertification: Assessing the Fit of Responses	EL	CP small/medium
	UNDESERT	Understanding and combating desertification to mitigate its impact on ecosystem services	DK	CP small/medium
ENV.2009.2.1.4.1	STEP	Status and Trends of European Pollinators	UK	CP small/medium
ENV.2009.2.1.6.2	FoResTTraC	Forest ecosystem genomics research: supporting Transatlantic Cooperation	FR	CSA
ENV.2009.2.2.1.5	FORCE	Future of Reefs in a Changing Environment (FORCE): An ecosystem approach to managing Caribbean coral reefs in the face of climate change	UK	CP Large
ENV.2009.2.2.1.6	DS ³ F	The Deep Sea & Sub-Sea-floor Frontier	DE	CSA
ENV.2009.4.2.3.1	POLICYMIX	Assessing the role of economic instruments in policy mixes for ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation (POLICYMIX)	NO	CP small/medium
ENV.2009.4.2.3.2	SPIRAL	Science-Policy Interfaces for Biodiversity: Research, Action, and Learning	UK	CP small/medium
ENV.2009.5.1.0.2	CONGRESS	Conservation Genetic Resources for Effective Species Survival	UK	CSA
ENV.2009.5.1.0.2	MarineTT	European Marine Research Knowledge Transfer and Uptake of Results	IE	CSA
2010				
ENV.2010.1.1.5-1	MedSea	MEDiterranean Sea Acidification under changing climate	ES	CP small/medium
ENV.2010.1.1.6-1	I-REDD+	Impacts of Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation and Enhancing Carbon Stocks	DK	CP small/medium
ENV.2010.2.1.1-1	AFROMAISON	Africa at meso-scale: adaptative and integrated Tools and strategies on natural resources management	BE	CP-FP-SICA
ENV.2010.2.1.4-1	FunDivEUROPE	Functional significance of forest biodiversity in Europe	DE	CP Large
ENV.2010.2.1.4-2	BiodivERsA2	Cooperation and shared strategies for biodiversity research programmes in Europe	FR	CSA
ENV.2010.2.1.4-3	KNEU	Developing a Knowledge Network for European expertise on biodiversity and ecosystem services to inform policy making economic sectors	DE	CSA
ENV.2010.2.1.4-4	EcoFINDERS	Ecological Function and Biodiversity Indicators in European Soils	FR	CP Large
ENV.2010.2.2.1-1	EURO-BASIN	European Union Basin-scale Analysis, Synthesis and Integration (EURO-BASIN)	DE*	CP Large
ENV.2010.2.2.1-2	GreenSeas	Development of global plankton data base and model system for eco-climate early warning	NO	CP small/medium

* Coordinating country has changed between submission and negotiation phases. Midtal and Euro-Basin are actually coordinated by the United Kingdom and Denmark, respectively.

APPENDIX 3

ROUGH FIGURES FOR THE NUMBER OF EVALUATED AND FUNDED PROJECTS, NUMBER OF PARTICIPATIONS, AND REQUESTED FUNDING

Temporal variation of the number of submitted and funded projects, across all sub-activities

NUMBER OF PROJECTS		2007	2008	2009	2010	TOTAL "ENVIRONMENT"
ENVIRONMENT (GENERAL)	Evaluated	594	425	273	334	1626
	Funded	74	68	63	70	275
	Success rate	12,5%	16,0%	23,1%	21,0%	16,9%
BIODIVERSITY	Evaluated	130	48	47	50	275
	Funded	14	9	12	9	44
	Success rate	10,8%	18,8%	25,5%	18,0%	16,0%
Biodiversity to Environment ratio	Evaluated	21,9%	11,3%	17,2%	15,0%	16,9%
	Funded	18,9%	13,2%	19,0%	12,9%	16,0%

Distribution of project number among sub-activities (2007-2010)

NUMBER OF PROJECTS		Pressures on environment and climate (ENV.1.1.)	Environment and health (ENV.1.2.)	Natural hazards (ENV.1.3.)	Sustainable management of resources (ENV.2.1.)	Marine environments (ENV.2.2.)	Environmental technologies (ENV.3.1.)	Cultural heritage (ENV.3.2.)	Technology assessment (ENV.3.3.)	Earth observation (ENV.4.1.)	Tools for sustainable development (ENV.4.2.)	Dissemination and horizontal activities (ENV.5.1.)	TOTAL "ENVIRONMENT" THEME
ENVIRONMENT (GENERAL)	Evaluated	193	129	133	299	68	366	107	32	83	153	63	1626
	Funded	38	24	16	32	19	49	15	10	25	33	14	275
	Success rate	19,7%	18,6%	12,0%	10,7%	27,9%	13,4%	14,0%	31,3%	30,1%	21,6%	22,2%	16,9%
BIODIVERSITY	Evaluated	21	4	4	133	55	14	0	2	13	21	8	275
	Funded	5	0	0	18	12	0	0	1	2	3	3	44
	Success rate	23,8%	0,0%	0,0%	13,5%	21,8%	0,0%	-	50,0%	15,4%	14,3%	37,5%	16,0%
Biodiversity to Environment ratio	Evaluated	10,9%	3,1%	3,0%	44,5%	80,9%	3,8%	0,0%	6,3%	15,7%	13,7%	12,7%	16,9%
	Funded	13,2%	0,0%	0,0%	56,3%	63,2%	0,0%	0,0%	10,0%	8,0%	9,1%	21,4%	16,0%

Distribution of participation numbers among sub-activities (2007-2010)

PARTICIPATIONS		Pressures on environment and climate (ENV.1.1.)	Environment and health (ENV.1.2.)	Natural hazards (ENV.1.3.)	Sustainable management of resources (ENV.2.1.)	Marine environments (ENV.2.2.)	Environmental technologies (ENV.3.1.)	Cultural heritage (ENV.3.2.)	Technology assessment (ENV.3.3.)	Earth observation (ENV.4.1.)	Tools for sustainable development (ENV.4.2.)	Dissemination and horizontal activities (ENV.5.1.)	TOTAL "ENVIRONMENT" THEME
ENVIRONMENT (GENERAL)	Evaluated	2390	1482	1534	3782	1025	4324	1321	415	1061	1315	478	19127
	Funded	667	289	244	492	351	729	224	137	357	300	132	3922
	Success rate	27,9%	19,5%	15,9%	13,0%	34,2%	16,9%	17,0%	33,0%	33,6%	22,8%	27,6%	20,5%
BIODIVERSITY	Evaluated	300	43	55	1649	798	123	0	20	163	221	54	3426
	Funded	79	0	0	288	217	0	0	10	40	33	25	692
	Success rate	26,3%	0,0%	0,0%	17,5%	27,2%	0,0%	-	50,0%	24,5%	14,9%	46,3%	20,2%
Biodiversity to Environment ratio	Evaluated	12,6%	2,9%	3,6%	43,6%	77,9%	2,8%	0,0%	4,8%	15,4%	16,8%	11,3%	17,9%
	Funded	11,8%	0,0%	0,0%	58,5%	61,8%	0,0%	0,0%	7,3%	11,2%	11,0%	18,9%	17,6%

Distribution of funding amounts among sub-activities (2007-2010)

FUNDING (K€)		Pressures on environment and climate (ENV.1.1.)	Environment and health (ENV.1.2.)	Natural hazards (ENV.1.3.)	Sustainable management of resources (ENV.2.1.)	Marine environments (ENV.2.2.)	Environmental technologies (ENV.3.1.)	Cultural heritage (ENV.3.2.)	Technology assessment (ENV.3.3.)	Earth observation (ENV.4.1.)	Tools for sustainable development (ENV.4.2.)	Dissemination and horizontal activities (ENV.5.1.)	TOTAL "ENVIRONMENT" THEME
ENVIRONMENT (GENERAL)	Evaluated	620 539	399 769	362 025	1 043 582	273 473	1 074 813	256 673	122 678	235 818	239 869	54 661	4 683 900
	Funded	155 184	76 710	51 469	121 992	89 197	157 197	32 568	36 831	78 041	54 091	14 667	867 947
	Success rate	25,0%	19,2%	14,2%	11,7%	32,6%	14,6%	12,7%	30,0%	33,1%	22,6%	26,8%	18,5%
BIODIVERSITY	Evaluated	92 196	13 993	16 256	467 902	225 386	38 811	0	6 033	38 655	43 300	7 879	950 412
	Funded	22 488	0	0	66 247	59 701	0	0	3 284	9 590	6 610	2 911	170 831
	Success rate	24,4%	0,0%	0,0%	14,2%	26,5%	0,0%	-	54,4%	24,8%	15,3%	36,9%	18,0%
Biodiversity to Environment ratio	Evaluated	14,9%	3,5%	4,5%	44,8%	82,4%	3,6%	0,0%	4,9%	16,4%	18,1%	14,4%	20,3%
	Funded	14,5%	0,0%	0,0%	54,3%	66,9%	0,0%	0,0%	8,9%	12,3%	12,2%	19,8%	19,7%

FRB's mission is to promote the French research on biodiversity in relation to the national, European and international contexts. As a member of the Environment National Contact Point for the Seventh Framework programme (FP7) for Research and Technological Development, the FRB is a link between the European Commission and the French research community in the field of biodiversity and natural resources, facilitating and analyzing the participation to the calls for proposal.

The "Environment" theme of the FP7 is considered as a major source of funding for biodiversity research at the European level. However, within this programme, biodiversity is a cross-disciplinary topic, funded through various pre-defined sub-activities. The FRB has used a set of indicators and data commonly used by the European Commission to analyse the success rate and funding of biodiversity projects within the "Environment" theme of the FP7 Cooperation programme over the 2007-2010 period. The main goal of the study is to assess the importance of biodiversity among the sub-activities of the FP7 "Environment" theme. The temporal trends of funding and success rate are also assessed over the 2007-2010 period, and the relative performances of the participating countries are compared.

The results of the study offer a key tool to understand the place of biodiversity and its recent trends within the "Environment" theme of the FP7.

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The FRB, Fondation pour la Recherche sur la Biodiversité (Foundation for Research on Biodiversity) was officially set up in 2008 by the French Ministry for Research and Ministry of the Environment. It was founded by eight public research institutes (BRGM, CEMAGREF, CIRAD, CNRS, IFREMER, INRA, IRD, MNHN) and is a meeting point for the various parties involved in the scientific community and in society. To date, more than 110 organisations, including wildlife conservation associations, businesses, natural resources managers and local authorities have joined the FRB.

THE FOUNDER MEMBERS OF THE FRB:

